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FAKE NEWS vs BAD NEWS in Media Discourse*lena Gryshchenko**PhD (Linguistics), Associate professor at English Language and Communication Department, Borys Grinchenko Kyiv University**Galyna Tsapro**PhD (Linguistics), Associate professor, Head of English Language and Communication Department, Borys Grinchenko Kyiv University*

The paper presents a trial stage of contrast research of FAKE NEWS and BAD NEWS collocations in media texts. The corpus of 10 “The Economist” issues published in January-April 2021 has been compiled. The corpus has been processed with the help of Sketch Engine program.

The methodology includes corpus and discourse analyses. Corpus analysis enables to single out the lemma FAKE, most frequent collocates with the lemma FAKE as well as synonyms or related words (the lemma BAD), and most frequent common collocate NEWS with both lemmas FAKE and BAD.

The thesaurus offers two options of synonyms and related words to the lemma FAKE in our corpus – false and fake (see Pic. 1).

	Word	Frequency ?
1	false	31 ...
2	bad	251 ...

Picture 1. Synonyms and related words to FAKE

The lemma BAD is taken for next stages of the study as the most frequent in the corpus and as it has a common collocate NEWS with the lemma FAKE (see Pic. 2).

Picture 2. Collocations with FAKE and BAD

NEWS proves to be the most frequently used noun modified by FAKE and BAD in newspaper texts (see Pic. 3).

certificate	2	0	...
divorce	1	0	...
shoe	1	0	...
personality	1	0	...
account	2	0	...
blood	1	1	...
news	12	8	...
publicity	0	2	...
nightmare	0	2	...
moment	0	3	...
thing	0	6	...
loan	0	4	...

Picture 3. Nouns modified by FAKE and BAD

The discourse analysis of the passages containing collocations FAKE NEWS and BAD NEWS allows to interpret news subjects where both collocations are used (see tables 1 and 2).

The following table presents the spheres that are covered in political stories in The Economist. The articles are devoted to the issue of jurisdiction, reporting on passing new laws for spreading fake news, paying fines for pieces of news which authorities consider to be fake, investigating cases of journalists being muzzled in authoritarian societies and introducing tougher censorship prohibiting points of view that do not coincide with governments' ones. Another field where FAKE NEWS is involved is cyber space and politics.

Table 1. FAKE NEWS: thematic representation

Subject		Examples
Internet	Wikipedia	Worries about fake news, filter bubbles and market power have soured public opinion ... Wikipedia's crowdsourced model remains vulnerable to the occasional hoaxer or chancer. ... Nor is it free from honest mistakes.
	Social-media sites	As social-media sites are lambasted for censorship, "fake news", disinformation and conspiracy theories
Elections	USA	Mr Trump has promoted conspiracies ... Thus, his claim that Barack Obama was born in Africa; his attacks on "fake news" and whatever "Deep State" agency or dutiful public servant impeded him; and his electoral-fraud delusion.
Jurisdiction	Law	Hong Kong's chief executive, Carrie Lam, is keen to pass a law to stop the dissemination of fake news after the protests that roiled the city in 2019. Governments have always regulated speech.
	Freedom of speech	If politicians are enacting laws against fake news to catch people spreading deliberate lies ... vague measures that are in fact intended to curb the freedom of the press and free speech
	Fines	Tatyana Voltskaya, ... was fined 30,000 roubles in December for a radio report ... the shortage of ventilators in Russian hospitals ... battling covid-19. Other governments are reviving obsolete legislation, ostensibly to combat fake news related to covid-19.
	Censorship	Germany's Network Enforcement Law, passed in 2017, is meant to protect readers from fake news and hate speech by requiring social-

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		media platforms to remove material deemed incendiary. More than a dozen countries, from Russia to Turkey, have copied this legislation as a way to suppress dissent online
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Table 2 demonstrates themes reflected in political stories which are related to BAD NEWS in The Economist. It includes the articles focusing on pandemic, world trade and elections. Pandemic is seen in terms of health issues, vaccination problems and management challenges. World trade comprises foreign policy and internal affairs including company policy. Election races in France contain a bad-news message for one of candidates who changes her point of view to get more electorate.

Table 2. BAD NEWS: thematic representation

Subject		Examples
Pandemic	Health	"We're going to see real complexity as more mutations accumulate in different combinations," she says. That may well be bad news for the virus' human hosts and the societies they comprise.
	Vaccination	Another study, in Scotland, included younger age groups and also found the two jabs had similar potency against hospitalisation. For a virus seeking new hosts, this is bad news – which will only get worse.
	Management	Many managers complain of "Zoom fatigue", as they drag themselves from one video-call to another, often keeping other participants waiting as they try to wrap up the previous meeting. This bad news has a silver lining. Get rid of the needless meetings and productivity should improve. The best habit developed during the pandemic has been flexibility.
World Trade	Foreign Policy	In his instincts about the economics of trade, America's new president is not so different from his predecessor. That is bad news for America and for the world.
	Company Policy	This month, after an auction of Sweden's 5g radio spectrum that forbade the winners from using kit from Huawei ... That would be bad news for Ericsson, which derives 13% of its revenues from China.
Elections	France	Marine Le Pen, a right-wing nationalist who had previously said she would wait and see before getting vaccinated now says she will do so ... The bad news about changing the weather in this sort of way is that it can quickly change back again.

Corpus-based discourse analysis allows to prove distinguishing features of FAKE and BAD which are verbalized differently in their thematic representation: FAKE NEWS is false and not true while BAD NEWS is not optimistic but based on the truth.